

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Umidbek Qodirov Urdu

NAZAR ESHONQUL IJODIDA MA'NAVYI-AXLOQIY MASALALAR

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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